

Title: Well-being, Social Integrity and Autonomy in Doctoral Education

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Indicate your track:

(Underline the track, which suits your abstract the most. You can select more than one track)

1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 1. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 2. Institutional interventions and policies
 3. Policy-Level insights
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Purpose

The well-being of doctoral candidates is increasingly at risk. Committed action is needed to turn the negative spiral in work stress and work pressure. In the Netherlands there is a discussion ongoing about the manner of accountability of academics, how they are appreciated in their work, and more specific the unhealthy competitiveness (e.g. how many articles you have published in high ranking journals or the amount of funding you have raised).

The purpose of this presentation is to give an overview of the institutional interventions and policies that are developed to stimulate well-being of doctoral candidates at one of the universities in the Netherlands: Utrecht University. For example the university board decided in 2021 on an additional focus in the yearly appraisal meeting for staff members: they are also evaluated on their supportive behavior (how they stimulate the wellbeing of team members) and on social integrity.

Design

In order to be able to give an overview of institutional interventions and policies to stimulate well-being of doctoral candidates online desk research was performed (without systematic methodology yet). In addition, interviews with PhD candidates were conducted to provide in-depth understanding.

Results

Both PhD candidates themselves and Utrecht university has taken initiatives to turn the negative spiral in work stress and work pressure. A few initiatives are listed below.

Bottom-up initiatives:

- The overall network of doctoral candidates in this specific university started with a survey on work-stress amongst doctoral candidates. The percentage of work-stress was extreme high. In research studies there exists confirmation of these high levels of work-stress and

work-pressure amongst doctoral candidates (Levecque, Anseel, De Beuckelaer, Van der Heyden & Gisle, 2017; Van der Weijden & Meijer, 2017). Also the risks of high levels of work-stress and work-pressure are investigated, like not finishing the doctoral thesis timely and drop-outs (Herfs, Brown, Farrell, & Meiser, 2019); burn-out and sick-leave (Van der Weijden & Meijer, 2017; Cornér, Pyhältö, Peltonen, & Löfström, 2021); and loosing research investments (Van de Schoot, Yerkes, Mouw & Sonneveld, 2013; Golde, 2005; Gardner, 2010).

- Every graduate school of one of the Dutch universities has a PhD-council and they have started their own working groups on mental well-being (surveys, urgency calls to the board and management, initiatives in retreats, presentations, workshops).

Top-down initiatives:

Based upon the above bottom-up initiatives and research outcomes Utrecht University needed to deal with problems and risks of well-being of their (young) researchers.

- The graduate schools of Humanities started with the function of a PhD-coach.
- Later followed with the function of PhD-psychologist for doctoral candidates for the whole university and the connected medical and research centers.
- The university medical center started with the function of PhD-confidential advisor and later other graduate schools followed.
- PhD-courses on soft skills to prevent ill-being and feeling of unsafety (given by the PhD-psychologist) were implemented via the graduate schools (with specific topics, like “Balance (coping with stress and pressure)”; “Resilience (coping with dependency)”; “Self-management (coping with procrastination)”; “Transparent communication & interaction”; and “Mindfulness”).
- This university is also one of the four “caring universities” in the Netherlands, which developed free online modules (with an online coach) to prevent ill-being. The topics are mood problems, anxiety, procrastination and coping with the corona-pandemic). These were first developed for bachelor and master students and since September also open for doctoral candidates.
- The Human Resources (HR) Developmental Guide provides courses and guided intervention for all employees (so also for supervisors and doctoral candidates).
- Courses for (starting) supervisors and masterclasses were developed and given.
- At university level a theater on integrity (“Mindlab”) was given for free to all employees – a confronting play based upon many interviews with academics. This has made very explicit the vulnerable and dependent position of doctoral candidates.

In addition, I recently started a PhD study on well-being of doctoral students. The overall research question is how do doctoral candidates develop their professional autonomy throughout their (international) doctoral education and how do they profit from autonomy support of their supervisors?

Why autonomy? Because autonomy is one of the core elements in (re)gaining mental well-being (Bohlmeijer, et al., 2016, Vendrig, 2016), and is highly related to intrinsic motivation and therefore work-pleasure (Deci, Connell & Ryan, 1989; Devos, Van der Linden, Boudrenghien, Azzi, Frenay, Galand, & Klein, 2015; Vakkaila & Pyhältö, 2016).

Implications

The results of my planned longitudinal in-depth interviews and surveys for doctoral candidates as well as (their) supervisors will be used to develop two types of training courses, one for doctoral candidates (gaining professional autonomy) and another for supervisors (autonomy-support). The effectivity of the courses will be tested by pre- and post-measurements using The Resilience Evaluation Scale (RES) of Van der Meer et al (2018), and the Autonomy-Connectedness Scale (ACS) of Bekkers et al (2016). This could provide evidence-based practices and guidelines (a guide for supervisors how to support autonomy doesn't exist yet (Barnard & Shultz, 2019).

Acknowledgments

Not applicable

Resources

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